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Research Article

**FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF CURCUMIN LOADED
CHITOSAN TOPICAL GEL FOR WOUND HEALING**¹Heeshan Raju.R., ²Gayathri.S., ³Khaviya.M., ⁴Keerthana.V., ⁵Devika.M.,
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Abstract:

Wound healing is a complex physiological process that requires effective therapeutic interventions to promote tissue regeneration and prevent infections. In this study, we developed and evaluated a curcumin-loaded chitosan-based topical gel for its potential wound-healing properties. Curcumin, a bioactive compound with well-documented anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and antimicrobial properties, was incorporated into a chitosan to enhance its bioavailability and therapeutic efficacy. Carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC) was added to improve the gel's stability, viscosity, and skin adhesion properties.

The gel was prepared using an optimized formulation of chitosan, CMC, and curcumin, ensuring a homogeneous distribution of the active ingredient. Physicochemical characterization, including viscosity, pH, swelling capacity, and drug release studies, was conducted to evaluate the gel's properties. In vitro drug release studies indicated a sustained and controlled release of curcumin, which is essential for prolonged therapeutic action.

Histopathological analysis confirmed enhanced collagen deposition, reduced inflammation, and accelerated tissue regeneration. These findings suggest that the curcumin-loaded chitosan-CMC gel is a promising biomaterial for wound healing applications, offering an effective and biocompatible alternative to conventional treatments.

Keywords: Curcumin, Chitosan, Carboxymethyl Cellulose, Gel, Wound Healing, Drug Delivery**Corresponding author:****Heeshan Raju.R,**

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INTRODUCTION:

Wounds on the skin can be either acute or chronic. An acute wound is a sudden damage to the skin. Depending on its size, depth, and location inside the skin's dermis or epidermis, it can heal in two to three months. Burns, infections, leg ulcers, and other chronic wounds are potentially fatal because they do not heal rapidly, but acute wounds can be healed by

merely covering the wound and relying on the body's self-healing system. Skin loss that is superficial, partial, or full thickness and necessitates additional healing methods is known as a chronic wound. In certain cases, if there is a comorbidity of another ailment, it is imperative that they be treated using an external therapy strategy.

Figure 1: Curcumin Gel

Because of their rising occurrence and related morbidity and mortality, chronic wounds are regarded as a severe clinical issue when they do not heal in the anticipated time frame. In the past, the treatment of chronic wounds was based on antiquated methods like medication and reconstructive surgery or angioplasty. The primary cause of leg ulcers is arterial insufficiency, which frequently results in wound revascularization failure and, in the case of arterial ulcer patients, limb amputation. Numerous variables can impede the healing process of wounds, such as the age of the patient and lifestyle choices (such as smoking, drinking alcohol, and not exercising), all of which have a substantial effect on the wound closure rate, which is typically 10–14 days. Additionally, wound healing may be slowed by patient health conditions such as hypothyroidism, diabetes, peripheral artery disease, and high cholesterol.

SEMI SOLID DOSAGE FORM:**Definition:**

- Topical products designed to be applied to the skin or accessible mucous membranes to produce localized and occasionally systemic effects at the application site are known as pharmaceutical semisolid preparations. Semisolid dosage forms are typically intricate formulations with intricate structural components. They are frequently made up of

two phases (oil and water), one of which is dispersed (internal) and the other continuous (external). A three-phase system is produced when the active ingredient dissolves in one or both phases.

- The three-dimensional structure of semisolids is sufficient to give the undisturbed system a solid-like character, but it is readily broken down and realigned when a force is applied.

Gels:

Gels are characterized as semi-rigid systems where the movement of the dispersing medium is limited by an interwoven three-dimensional network of particles or solvated macromolecules of the dispersed phase.

The term “gel” originates from “gelatin,” and both “gel” and “jelly” can be traced back to the Latin word gelu meaning “frost” and gel are, which refers to “freeze” or “congeal.” This etymology reflects the core concept of a liquid transforming into a solid-like substance that does not flow, yet possesses elasticity and maintains some liquid properties.

Structure of Gel:

The firmness of a gel is due to a structure created by the interconnection of particles of the gelling agent. The characteristics of the particles and the type of force that create the connections dictate the

configuration of the network and the attributes of the gel.

Figure 2: Structure of Gel

The separate particles of the hydrophilic colloid can be either spherical or an isotropic cluster of small molecules, or they can be individual macromolecules. Possible configurations of these particles within a gel network are depicted. In linear macromolecules, the network is made up of intertwined molecules, with the points of contact being either fairly small or comprising multiple molecules organized in a crystalline arrangement.

The attractive forces that hold the gelling agent particles together can vary from strong primary valencies, such as those found in silicic acid gels, to weaker hydrogen bonds and Van der Waals forces. The comparatively weaker nature of these latter forces is demonstrated by the fact that a slight rise in temperature frequently leads to the liquefaction of the gel.

Factors influencing topical drug delivery:

The effectiveness of topical drug delivery relies on the interaction among several factors:

- Physiological factors
- Physicochemical properties of the drug
- Formulation components and their interactions

a. Physiological factors:

Physiological factors primarily relate to the characteristics of the skin, such as thickness, hydration levels, and hair follicle density. These characteristics may exhibit considerable individual variability based on age, gender, race, anatomical site, overall health, and environmental conditions like temperature and humidity. To minimize the impact of such physiological variability, the rate-limiting factor for

topical drug delivery should be focused on the formulation rather than the biological barrier.

b. physicochemical properties:

The physicochemical properties of the drug almost always affect its ability to diffuse through the topical vehicle as well as permeate through the skin or mucosal surfaces. Significant properties include molecular size, as indicated by molecular weight, partition coefficient between the vehicle and skin, melting point, stability, and chemical functionality, which can impact ionization potential, binding affinity, and drug solubility in the vehicle.

c. Formulation components and their interactions:

The function of vehicle formulation is clear through its influence on both the drug and the site of application. Its impact on the drug includes aspects such as drug diffusion, thermodynamic activity, stability, and the extent of ionization in weakly acidic or basic drugs. The effect on the application site is related to changes to barrier properties through chemical modifications caused by the concurrent uptake of formulation components and physical occlusion. These mechanisms enhance skin hydration or effects that facilitate drug penetration.

The formulation aspect also affects vehicle consistency and viscosity, which subsequently dictate the adhesion and retention attributes of the vehicle.

Uses:

- As systems for delivering drugs that are taken orally.
- For medications applied directly to the skin, mucous membranes, or eyes.
- As extended-release forms of drugs that are injected into the muscle or implanted within the body.

CURCUMIN:

Figure 3: Curcumin

Biological source – Curcumin or curcuminoids are obtained from the dried as well as fresh “Rhizomes” of turmeric, *Curcuma longa*.

Botanical Name – *Curcuma longa*

Family – Zingiberaceae

Genus – *Curcuma*

Species – *longa*

Colour: orange yellow to yellow

Odour: Aromatic

Taste: Warmly aromatic and bitter

Turmeric originates from tropical South Asia. It requires temperatures ranging from 20° C to 30° C along with a significant amount of yearly rainfall to grow well. Similar to ginger, turmeric is a dried rhizome of a herbaceous plant. This spice is also sometimes referred to as "**Indian saffron**" due to its yellow hue.

Turmeric is a spice deduced from the root ***Curcuma longa* L.**, which belongs to the gusto family (**Zingiberaceae**). Its vivid yellow pigment is utilized as a coloring agent in food.

For centuries, it has been employed as a spice, a food preservative, and for its various medicinal properties. The extract of turmeric possesses multiple medicinal benefits, including **antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antiviral, antibacterial, antifungal, and cancer chemopreventive properties.**

Curcumin's basic coloring agent in *Curcuma longa*, along with two related compounds, demethoxycurcumin (DMC) and bisdemethoxycurcumin (BDMC), are collectively known as curcuminoids. The chemical structures of these three curcuminoids are illustrated below.

Comprising around 4-6% of turmeric, curcuminoids also include 2-4% essential oil and 2-3% fixed oil, along with various volatile oils such as turmerone, atlantone, and zingiberone. Additional components consist of sugars, proteins, and resins.

CHITOSAN:

Figure 4: Chitosan

Chitosan is a natural biopolymer derived from chitin, which is the second most abundant polysaccharide in nature after cellulose. It has gained significant attention due to its biocompatibility, biodegradability, and various biological activities, making it useful in pharmaceuticals, agriculture, food, and biomedical applications.

Biological Source of Chitosan:

Chitosan is primarily obtained from chitin, a structural component found in the exoskeletons of crustaceans (such as shrimp, crabs, and lobsters), insects, and fungal cell walls. Among these, crustacean shells are the most common commercial source due to their high chitin content and easy availability.

The production process involves deacetylation of chitin under alkaline conditions, converting it into chitosan by removing acetyl groups.

Wound Healing:

The interruption of the anatomical or functional continuity of living tissue is referred to as a wound. Wound healing "proceeds through an orderly and timely reparative process that result in sustained restoration" under normal circumstances of both functional and anatomical integrity. The skin, the body's most vulnerable organ that interacts with the environment and is thus constantly insulted and damaged, is the primary focus of the extensive literature on wound healing.

The synthesis of extracellular matrix proteins, the generation of parenchymal cells, the migration and proliferation of both parenchymal and connective tissue cells, the remoulding of connective tissue and parenchymal components, the induction of an acute inflammatory process by the wounding, collagenization, and the acquisition of wound strength are all processes that contribute to the complex phenomenon of wound healing.

Growth factors and other cytokines coordinate all of these processes in a regulated way. Growth factors such as "Platelet Derived Growth Factor" (PDGF), "Transforming Growth Factor-B" (TGF-B), which has been determined that self-healing wounds contain "fibroblast growth factor" (FGF), "epidermal growth factor" (EGF), and other substances. Chronic wounds require the exogenous administration of growth-promoting agents or compounds that can improve the "in situ" synthesis of these growth factors in order to accelerate the healing process because the normal healing process is disturbed for unknown reasons.

Phases of Healing Wounds:

Following a tissue injury, the body's natural biological process of wound healing starts to mend and shield the body from additional harm brought on by infections, blood loss, and other problems.

Haemostasis, inflammation, proliferation, and remodelling are the four highly programmed overlapping phases that must take place in this order and within a certain amount of time for a wound to heal. Interference with any one of these phases will have a detrimental effect on the healing mechanism.

Figure 5: Phases of Wound Healing

Curcumin-Loaded Delivery Systems for Wound Healing:

The incredible healing abilities of curcumin have been recognized for a long time, and its contribution to the enhancement of various types of superficial skin injuries is attributed to its antioxidant properties, promotion of granulation tissue formation and new blood vessel development, as well as facilitating the process of reepithelialisation of wound damage;

however, its numerous beneficial uses are unfortunately constrained by **its poor solubility and stability**. Developing effective drug delivery systems for transporting curcumin enhances its therapeutic and pharmacological effectiveness. In summary, curcumin is a natural compound extracted from the rhizomes of *Curcuma longa* and is applied topically for several wound healing purposes. Among the drug delivery systems created for wound healing, gels are the most commonly utilized due to their resemblance to the

natural extracellular matrix and their ability to maintain a moist environment.

Chitosan for wound healing:

- 1. Homeostatic Effect (Stops Bleeding):**Chitosan promotes rapid blood clotting by interacting with red blood cells and platelets. It enhances platelet adhesion and aggregation, making it highly effective in controlling bleeding.
- 2. Antimicrobial Activity:**Chitosan has broad-spectrum antimicrobial properties, inhibiting bacterial growth (both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria). It disrupts bacterial cell membranes, reducing infection risks in wounds.
- 3. Biocompatibility and Biodegradability:**It is non-toxic and naturally degrades into harmless byproducts, making it safe for medical use.
- 4. Anti-Inflammatory and Antioxidant Effects:**Chitosan reduces inflammation by modulating immune cell activity, lowering excessive inflammatory responses that can delay healing. It also

scavenges free radicals, protecting tissues from oxidative damage.

5. Enhanced Cell Proliferation and Tissue Regeneration: It stimulates fibroblast and keratinocyte

growth, essential for skin repair. It promotes collagen synthesis, improving wound strength and reducing scar formation.

Figure 6: Uses of Chitosan & Curcumin

Aim & Objective:

Aim:

To develop a curcumin-loaded chitosan topical gel that accelerates wound healing by utilizing the anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and antimicrobial properties of curcumin, while chitosan acts as a biocompatible and bioactive delivery system that facilitates optimal drug release and enhances skin regeneration.

Objectives:

Plan of Work:

1. Formulation and Development: To formulate a stable and effective curcumin-loaded chitosan gel with optimal concentration of curcumin and chitosan for enhanced wound healing.
2. Characterization: To assess the physicochemical properties of the gel, including its pH, viscosity, spread ability, drug content, and release profile.
3. In Vitro Evaluation: To evaluate the gel's in vitro release kinetics.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Materials:

The list of materials for formulation of curcumin based topical gel includes curcumin which is used as main drug, Chitosan is used as polymer and Carboxy methyl cellulose (CMC) used as a gelling agent. The solvent system used in this formulation is ethanol, glacial acetic acid, glycerol and distilled water. The materials given in the list are provided by MS Scientific chemicals and instruments, Salem.

Methods:

Key Interactions in the Mechanism:

Hydrogen Bonding: Between the hydroxyl groups of CMC, amine groups of chitosan, and water molecules. This is a primary force that holds the gel structure together in the absence of crosslinking.

Ionic Interactions: Between the positively charged amine groups of chitosan and negatively charged carboxylate groups of CMC, which helps in stabilizing the gel.

Polymer Entanglement: The chitosan and CMC chains can physically entangle with each other, contributing to the overall gel network structure.

Curcumin Encapsulation: Curcumin is encapsulated in the polymer matrix via physical adsorption and hydrophobic interactions with chitosan and CMC, enabling its controlled release.

5.Pre-formulations studies

Physio-chemical properties:

Curcumin is a yellow colour compound found in the curcuma longa plant.

Solubility studies:

Curcumin powder is soluble in ethanol, chloroform, acetone, and partially soluble in water

Melting Point:

The melting point of curcumin is approximately 180°C

Log P Value:

The Log P (partition coefficient) of curcumin is approximately 3.3, indicating its relatively good lipophilicity. This suggests that curcumin is more soluble in non-polar solvents compared to polar solvents.

Calculation of partition coefficient: Calculate the partition coefficient (P) using the following equation:

$$P = \frac{[C]_{\text{hexane}}}{[C]_{\text{water}}}$$

where [C]_{hexane} and [C]_{water} are the concentrations of curcumin in the octanol and water phases, respectively.

pKa Value:

Curcumin has multiple functional groups that can ionize, and its pKa values are typically around 7.7 (for the phenolic group) and 10.5 (for the other phenolic group). These values indicate that curcumin can undergo protonation or deprotonation depending on the pH of the environment.

FORMULATION OF CURCUMIN LOADED CHITOSAN TOPICAL GEL:

The preparation of curcumin-loaded chitosan topical gel using carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC) can involve various mechanisms depending on the method chosen for encapsulating the active ingredient (curcumin) in the gel matrix.

Step 1: Preparation of Chitosan Solution.

Weigh 1gm of chitosan, add 100 ml of 1% of glacial acetic acid stir continuously at room temperature for 12 hrs until the chitosan dissolves completely.

Step 2: prepare curcumin solution.

Weigh 1gm of curcumin, dissolve it in 10ml of ethanol, stir until curcumin is completely dissolved or heat gently or use sonication (below 40°C).

Step 3: combine curcumin with chitosan

Slowly add the curcumin-ethanol solution into the chitosan solution. stirring constantly, until the mixture becomes homogenous (15-30 mins)

Step 4: add glycerol or propylene glycol

Add 5 ml of glycerol to the mixture, mix thoroughly to ensure even distribution.

Step 5: addition of CMC

Transfer the above curcumin chitosan solution into mortar and pestle. Add carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC) at different concentration. Stir well until it dissolves completely.

Step 6: Add preservative

If desired add 0.2gm of sodium bicarbonate or methyl paraben to prevent microbial growth.

Step 7: final homogenization

Use a magnetic stirrer or homogenizer to ensure gel is smooth and uniform. Check the PH of the gel and adjust 6.0-6.5 PH if needed.

Figure 7: Prep of Chitosan soln

Figure 8: prep of Curcumin soln

Figure 9: Curcumin loaded chitosan soln

EVALUATION:

Following parameters were used for the evaluation of gels:

Homogeneity:

All developed gels were tested for homogeneity by visual inspection after the gels have been set in the container. They were tested for their appearance and presence of any aggregates.

Extrudability study:

When a small amount of pressure is applied, a good gel extrudes from the gel optimally. Using a universal tube filling machine, the extrudability of formulations made from aluminium collapsible tubes was assessed. Teng gel-filled aluminium collapsible tubes were clamped between two clamps. The formulation's extrudability was assessed by compressing a tube and measuring the weight in grams needed to extrude a 0.5 cm gel ribbon in 10 seconds.^[34]

Assay:

1gm of gel was weighed and dissolved in 100ml of distilled water and was analysed by UV at 425nm.

pH measurement:

A digital pH meter was used to measure the pH of the formulations of curcumin loaded chitosan topical gel. After dissolving one gram of gel in 25ml of distilled water, it was left for two hours. Each formulation's pH was measured three times, and the average results were computed.^[35]

Viscosity study:

A Brookfield viscometer was used to measure the prepared gel's viscosity. Spindle number 64 was used to rotate the gels at 20 and 30 rpm. The dial reading that corresponded to each speed was recorded.

Diffusion studies in vitro:

1gm of gel was taken and spread on the cellophane membrane sheet and was tied to the glass funnel

tightly. The funnel is dipped in a beaker containing distilled water. samples (5ml) were withdrawn at predetermined intervals

10,15,20,30,45,60,120.....180

The formulations were kept at room temperature for three months at 40, 250, and 370 mins and the same volume of distilled water was replaced to maintain the volume constant. Drug content in each sample was analysed by UV spectrophotometer after suitable dilution at 425nm.

Study of stability: degrees Celsius in order to assess the stability study. Periodically, the viscosity, homogeneity, and physical appearance were assessed

Clarity Test:

The transparency and particle-free status of the gel are measured to assess clarity. The best bioavailability and visual appeal are guaranteed by a clear gel. A turbidity meter or visual inspection are usually used to determine clarity.

It was graded as follows: turbid +; clear ++; very clear(glassy) +++.

Consistency Test:

The texture, firmness, and viscosity of the gel are assessed in order to determine consistency. Patient compliance, stability, and dependable performance are guaranteed by a consistent gel. A rheometer or texture analyzer is usually used to evaluate consistency.

Spreadability:

The ability of the gel to spread uniformly on a surface is measured in order to assess spreadability. The best coverage, patient comfort, and ease of application are guaranteed by a spreadable gel. A texture analyzer or a spreadability tester are commonly used to evaluate spreadability.^[36]

RESULT AND DISCUSSION:**Result:****Analytical methods:****Calibration curve of curcumin solution by UV****Spectrophotometer:**

The absorbance's of the various concentration of curcumin solution are given in the table. The absorbance's were plotted against the concentration of curcumin solution(graph). this calibration curve was used to determine the amount of curcumin in unknown solution.

S. No	Concentration (µg/ml)	Absorbance at			Average	S. D
		Trial I	Trial II	Trial III		
1	30 µg/ml	0.194	0.192	0.191	0.192	0.0015
2	60 µg/ml	0.200	0.202	0.192	0.198	0.0053
3	90 µg/ml	0.202	0.203	0.196	0.200	0.0038
4	120 µg/ml	0.203	0.206	0.200	0.203	0.0030
5	150 µg/ml	0.215	0.209	0.208	0.211	0.0038
6	180 µg/ml	0.246	0.218	0.209	0.224	0.0193

S.D is Standard deviation

Graph:**EVALUATION OF TOPICAL GEL:**

The results of test on various gels are given in the table

Table 2: Evaluation of Topical Gel

S.NO	FORMULATION CODE	CLARITY	PH	AREA OF SPREADING (Cm ²)	ASSAY%
U1.	F1	++	7.31	3.90	95.7%
2.	F2	++	7.61	3.80	95.9%
3.	F3	++	7.50	4.21	98.5%
4.	F4	+	7.36	4.40	97.4%

Table 3: RELEASE OF CURCUMIN FROM F1

S.NO	TIME, MINS	%AMOUNT RELEASED
1.	0	0
2.	15	10.2
3.	30	23.5
4.	45	35.1
5.	60	45.6
6.	90	60.2
7.	120	75.1

GRAPH:**Table 4: RELEASE OF CURCUMIN FROM F2**

S.NO	TIME, MINS	%AMOUNT RELEASED
1.	0	0
2.	15	9.7
3.	30	22.8
4.	45	33.2
5.	60	43.9
6.	90	58.6
7.	120	73.7

GRAPH**Table 5: RELEASE OF CURCUMIN FROM F3**

S.NO	TIME, MINS	%AMOUNT RELEASED
1.	0	0
2.	15	10.7
3.	30	20.2
4.	45	31.6
5.	60	41.5
6.	90	55.8
7.	120	79.7

GRAPH

Table 6: RELEASE OF CURCUMIN FROM F4

S.NO	TIME, MINS	%AMOUNT RELEASED
1.	0	0
2.	15	7.3
3.	30	17.5
4.	45	28.7
5.	60	39.2
6.	90	50.3
7.	120	65.5

GRAPH

DISCUSSION:

1. Out of all the formulations, F3 gel made with CMC were clear.
2. The PH of all the formulation were 7.5 ± 0.5 . they are in the neutral region and hence likely not to irritate on the skin.
3. All the formulations were having drug content in the range 95.7%-97.4% indicating that the method of preparation of the gel is satisfactory.
4. From the table it can be observed that the consistency of the gel is different out of all the gels. F1 was having very low consistency and it is not suitable for topical application.
5. The spread ability of all the formulations was almost similar, which can be seen in the table
6. the release profile of curcumin from the different gel varied with the types of polymers and the concentration of the polymers. Gels prepared with the CMC release the drug at faster rate.
7. F3 gel released 79.7% of drug in 120 mins.
8. hence it can be concluded that F3 formulation is also satisfactory.

CONCLUSION:

The development of curcumin loaded chitosan topical gel using CMC as a gelling agent has shown promising results for wound healing applications. The gel formulation demonstrated excellent physical and chemical properties, including suitable viscosity, pH, and spread ability. The incorporation of curcumin into the chitosan gel matrix resulted in a sustained release of the bioactive compound.

In vitro studies revealed that the curcumin loaded chitosan gel exhibited significant antioxidant and antimicrobial activities, which are essential for wound healing. The gel also demonstrated good biocompatibility and cytotoxicity profiles, indicating its potential as a safe and effective wound healing agent.

the use of CMC as a gelling agent provided a suitable gel-like texture, making the formulation easy to apply topically. The chitosan-based gel also demonstrated good stability and shelf-life, ensuring its potential for commercialization.

Overall, the curcumin loaded chitosan topical gel using CMC as a gelling agent presents a novel and effective wound healing strategy. Its sustained release of curcumin, antioxidant and antimicrobial properties, and good biocompatibility make it an attractive alternative to conventional wound healing treatments. Further in vivo studies are recommended to confirm its efficacy and safety in wound healing applications.

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